

ERRORS OF NUMERICAL INTEGRATION BY USE OF TABLE LOOK-UP

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INTRODUCTION

In a classical electromagnetic problem it is often required to compute the radiation field either radiated directly from a known current source or scattered from a secondary source. In general this leads to the evaluation of an integral of the form

$$F(\theta, \phi) = k \int f(\xi, \eta) \exp[jG(\xi, \eta, \phi, \theta)] d\xi d\eta \quad (1)$$

where ξ, η are the coordinates of the current source; ϕ and θ are the coordinates of a field point. In general the current distribution and the geometry of the source or scatterers are very complicated. This integration is usually performed numerically with a digital computer. Although it is straightforward to program such an integration, the required computer time may sometimes be extremely lengthy. In general, computations of the cosine and sine functions used in this integral are time consuming for a digital computer. One of the simplest approaches to reduce the required computer time is table look-up. In this approach, cosine and sine functions with a 2π period are computed and stored at the beginning of the computer program using an adequate number of sampling points. In later computations, the required cosine and sine functions are found from the table, thus avoiding the repeated computation of such functions. However, unless the arguments of these cosine and sine functions coincide with the sampling points in the table, errors will be introduced. The amount of error is a function of the number of sampling points in this cosine and sine table. In this paper the relationship between the errors and the table size will be discussed. Criteria for design of such a table will be presented.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

For a numerical integration, equation (1) can be transformed into the following form:

$$F(\theta, \phi) = \sum_n A_n \exp(jG_n) \quad (2)$$

where $A_n = f(\eta_n, \xi_n) \geq 0$

$$G_n = G(\eta_n, \xi_n, \theta_n, \phi_n)$$

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For simplification, the double summation of n and ξ in equation (1) is converted into a single summation index. The function $F(\theta, \phi)$ is a complex function having both real and imaginary components. When table look-up is used to determine the phase of the experimental term, errors are introduced and equation (1) becomes

$$F(\theta, \phi) = \sum_n A_n \exp(jG_n) \exp(j\delta_n) \quad (3)$$

$$= x + jy$$

where δ_n is the phase error due to table look-up. Function $F(\theta, \phi)$ is a random function with normal distribution. It can be shown that

$$p(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \left[(x-\bar{x})^2 + (y-\bar{y})^2 \right] \right\} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\sigma^2 \approx \frac{1}{2} (1 - |\phi(1)|^2) \sum_n A_n^2 \quad (5)$$

and $\phi(1)$ is the characteristic function of the phase error δ_n . This equation implies that the real and imaginary components of $F(\theta, \phi)$ are two independent variables and have the same variance. If the entries of the cosine and sine table are sampled uniformly within 2π range having a total number of sample points K , then $\alpha = 2\pi/K$ and

$$\bar{x} \approx (1 - .042\alpha^2) \text{RE} \sum_n A_n \exp(G_n) \quad (6)$$

$$\bar{y} \approx (1 - .042\alpha^2) \text{IM} \sum_n A_n \exp(G_n) \quad (7)$$

If the table has enough sampling points and α is small, then the $.042\alpha^2$ term can be ignored, and x and y are equal to the real and imaginary components of $f(\theta, \phi)$. The probability density functions of x and y can be written separately

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp \left[-\frac{(x-\bar{x})^2}{2\sigma^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$p(y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp \left[-\frac{(y-\bar{y})^2}{2\sigma^2} \right]$$

It can be shown that

$$\sigma = 1.28/K \sqrt{\sum_n A_n^2} \quad (9)$$

Eq. (10) relates the table size K to the standard deviation σ . Since $|x-x| \leq 3\sigma$ with probability higher than .99, if one should require that the x or y values should not deviate from the actual value by an amount ϵ with a probability of at least .99, the number of entries K in the table should be

$$K > \frac{3.85}{\epsilon} \sum_n A_n^2. \quad (10)$$

The values of A_n in eq. (10) are the amplitudes of the current distribution. These A_n are not known in general a priori. However, one may assume that all A_n are equal and that they are normalized such that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_n A_n &= 1 \\ \text{then } \sum_n A_n^2 &= \frac{1}{N} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

for a first order estimate. The number N is the total number of terms summed in eq. (4). Eq. (11) thus becomes

$$K > \frac{3.85}{\epsilon} \sqrt{1/N}. \quad (12)$$

One may notice that $\sum_n A_n$ represents the maximum value of x and y . When it is normalized to be unity, the desired error ϵ in eq. (13) can be set with respect to this level. For example, if one requires that a computed antenna pattern to be accurate to -60 dB, one must set $\epsilon = 10^{-3}$.

ESTIMATION OF AMPLITUDE AND PHASE ERRORS

In the previous section we showed the relationship between the table size K and the achievable accuracy of the real and imaginary parts of the scattering integral, eq. (3). However, we would also like to know what are the amplitude and phase deviations.

The statistical distribution of the function $F(\theta, \phi)$ is shown in Fig. 1. Point 0 represents the mean values $\bar{x}$ and $\bar{y}$, which are approximately equal to the true value of the real and imaginary components of $F(\theta, \phi)$ when phase error is small. With a probability of .99, all points of $R = |F(\theta, \phi)|$ lies within a circle with a radius of 3σ and centered at point 0 $(\bar{x}, \bar{y})$. It is evident that the maximum R is

$$R_{\max} = \bar{R} + 3\sigma$$

and minimum R is

$$R_{\min} = \bar{R} - 3\sigma$$

where $\bar{R} = \sqrt{\bar{x}^2 + \bar{y}^2}$, and σ is defined in eq. (5).

The maximum deviation of $|F(\theta, \phi)|$ is similar to that of its real and imaginary components. Therefore, the same error estimation shown in eq. (12) can be used in this case.

The phase deviation angle Δ is

$$\Delta = \tan^{-1}$$

$$\text{and } \phi_{\max} = \phi + \bar{\Delta}$$

$$\phi_{\min} = \phi - \bar{\Delta}$$

where

$$\phi = \tan^{-1}$$

The phase error is measured as the ratio of $\bar{R}$ and 3σ . If $\bar{R}$ is very small, phase error introduced by table look-up can be significant.

CONCLUDING COMMENT

Numerical examples simulated on a digital computer confirm the accuracy of this predicted error.

Fig. 1